

STUDY OF ABBREVIATIONS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS (SLANGS)

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ABSTRACT: this article provides full information about the linguistic features of the general concepts of the study of abbreviations in linguistics (slangs) and is one of the tools of image and expression in the field of study of abbreviations in linguistics (slangs) . It is the discovery of phenomena, which consists in making a scientific conclusion and giving a wider understanding to the information about images and means of expression.

Key words: slangs, phonetic, lexical, lexicography, semantics, dictionary.

Linguists know that words are the most basic and central unit of language. The sum of each word in our language and their vocabulary, internal and external possibilities are considered as the object of various fields. In particular, the phonetic possibilities of words are studied in the phonetics department, while the formal and semantic structure of words is reflected in the lexicology department.

The task of the lexicography department is to study the vocabulary of the word. A dictionary is a set of words collected and arranged for a purpose. It should be noted here that "the task of lexicography is to develop the principles and methodology of dictionary compilation, to organize the work of lexicographers, to create and systematize and maintain card files that serve as a basis for dictionary compilation..

It should also be noted that abbreviations in lexicographic sources are very important and of great practical importance. Various abbreviations found in all types of dictionaries help the lexicographer greatly in saving words and space. "Abbreviation, which first appeared in English in the 16th century to achieve economy in writing, first appeared in spoken speech, and then gradually began to move to written speech."

If a word is abbreviated by more than one letter and is originally written in lowercase letters, it does not need to be capitalized. However, when only the first letter of each word abbreviates the resulting phrase, all letters are capitalized. Abbreviation of capital letters used in the names of offices,

institutions, organizations or countries consisting of several words is one of the most common abbreviations.

In the textbook "Sovremenniy russkiy yazik" to abbreviation: "Among compound words, short compound words, that is, abbreviations occupy the main place. The method of creating abbreviated compound words is called abbreviation. "The formation of a word by the method of abbreviation is valid only within the group of nouns". In addition, V. Nemchenko's 1984 textbook "Contemporary Russian Language" and N. Valgina, D. Rosenthal, M.I. Fomina's 2002 textbook "Sovremenniy Russian Language" define abbreviation as a method of word formation.

So, to make our point, an acronym is a shortened form of a certain word or phrase. Abbreviations can be found in every language or come from other languages with the meaning understood and have their place in our speech. It is permissible to admit that abbreviations are artificial words. With the introduction of new words into our language, that is, at the expense of words acquired from other languages, the vocabulary of the language continues to develop in connection with the development of society.

In fact, according to the research conducted within this topic, abbreviations were found in the first sources of Sumerian culture, and in ancient Eastern manuscripts, abbreviations were used to simplify letters. Greek abbreviations are found in the sources of the 3rd century BC. With the introduction of the Latin alphabet in ancient Rome, Latin abbreviations appeared; they still participate as a constituent component in the composition of terms related to various fields of science". Although abbreviations appeared long ago, their linguistic study began after the 50s of the 20th century. Until now, this linguistic phenomenon and the linguistic features of the units that represent it have been studied on the example of functional styles of different languages.

It is not an exaggeration to say that the history of abbreviations and combinations was formed with the appearance of writing for the first time. A number of advanced scholars have expressed their valuable opinions that the process of shortening the word and using it as a noun began in the language of the Ancient Sumerians in the IV century BC, and it was actively used in Ancient Greece in the III-II centuries BC.

Based on the above-mentioned sources, from the early Middle Ages (V-XI), abbreviations began to be widely used in almost all existing languages. Especially in the European region, people who speak Latin are a minority, but its abbreviations are actively used in French, English and other languages. It was

also observed that this process was used in the Eastern countries, including in the Arabic language, which was at a high level of science at that time, as well as in the Turkish and Iranian languages based on the Arabic script. The fact that many abbreviations are found in the manuscripts of the works that have reached our time serves as a clear proof of our opinion.

If we explain this situation, referring to history, many works need to be quickly and beautifully copied by several master calligraphers in several copies, moreover, the works created with abbreviations are mostly people with very advanced knowledge. It is appropriate to emphasize that it was used for As mentioned above, it was also widely used in general communication and correspondence. Over the next several decades, the increasing desire to learn the language based on the human factor, in addition to the function of abbreviations to convey important information, the possibilities of expression related to the personality of the speaker and the speech situation, the expressive effect opportunities are also being identified. Therefore, abbreviations are used in the texts as a stylistic figure that shows the above possibilities.

In particular, the researches of O. Kosarev, D. Dunyova and M. Nechepurenko are devoted to the study of the same features of abbreviations in journalistic texts. It is said that the increase in the volume of information in a certain text serves as a means of expressive influence. Or we can note that additional connotativeness and puns are created by creating abbreviations that correspond to Russian words in form.

So, based on the sources, the word "abbreviation" – "abbreviation" in Italian was formed through the Latin verb "abbreviation" - "abbreviation" and the word "abbreviation" through the Italian language. It has entered all languages as a general concept denoting abbreviations and combinations. Abbreviation is also defined as "removing several letters from a word", that is, it is interpreted as an abbreviation formed by taking a series of basic letters that make up a word.

This method is usually formed from several consecutive letters of the word. This abbreviation is also distinguished by the use of a period. For example, a. - Arabic language, and g - gram, nm - nanometer (one millionth of a meter), t/o - intravenously, AG - hepatitis A, VG - hepatitis V, etc. – and similar (s), e.g. - for example, etc. These types of abbreviations are mainly found in dictionaries, scientific works, etc. are widely used and are also called "conditional abbreviations" in Uzbek.

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